

IS LYING EVER JUSTIFIED?

By

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INTRODUCTION

God is truth and every truth flows from the very nature of God. Since God is absolute truth, he always speaks and acts in truth (Num 23:19). He expects that his people should always speak the truth (Zech 8:16, Prov 12:17, and Eph 4:15). God hates all forms of lying, it is an abomination to him (Prov 12:22), he hates the people who bear false witnesses (Exod 20:16), and he will judge all the sinful liars (Rev 21:8, 1 Cor 6:9-10). Therefore, a lie is not acceptable to him because it is contrary to his nature. On the other hand, it is Satan who is the father of lies, deception, hatred, and maliciousness (John 8:44). However, there are instances in the Bible where people lied to protect life (Exod 1:17-20), support God's people (Josh 2), and to protect one's own life (2 Kgs 6:19). Bible did not condemn them for these lies. Instead, God showed favor to midwives (Exod 1:20) and the author of Hebrews appreciated the faith of Rahab (Heb 11:31). This raises some questions— is lying ever justified and what is a lie?

In this paper, I argue that lying can be permitted in some circumstances when we are not expected to tell the truth.¹ However, we should be cautious in not endorsing a lie for the sake of personal interests, to cover sins, to fulfill selfish mottos, to pursue evil and deception, and to oppress people. An argument can be made to permit a lie in order to obey God, protect lives, and fulfill a higher good. In this paper, first, I will provide definition of lie and support my argument with the writings of evangelical authors and scripture analysis. At last, I will also discuss the views which do not support lies under any circumstances.

¹ John Jefferson Davis. *Evangelical Ethics: Issues Facing the Church Today*, 4th ed. (Phillipsburg, New Jersey: P&R Publishing, 2015), 11.

First, the word “lie” should be carefully defined to avoid confusion with falsehood, deception, and tricks. Charles Hodge suggested that not every act of deception is a lie in terms of morality. According to him, a lie includes an intention to deceive when we are supposed and bound to tell the truth.² Full disclosure is not always expected, and a trick or deception is inevitable. For example, a sportsperson is not always bound to reveal his game. Rahab had no obligation to speak the truth when she is under the authority of a new King.³ In a similar vein, Sam Storms argued that not all falsehoods are lies. According to him, a lie is an intentional deception that disregards someone’s right to know the truth. In times of war and criminal assaults, we are not obligated to tell the truth to the enemy. He defined a lie as follows: “a lie is the intentional declaration or communication of a falsehood designed to deceive someone who has a moral and legal right to know the truth.”⁴ On the other hand, Grudem pointed out that “lying is affirming in a speech or writing something you believe to be false.”⁵

Second, scriptures reveal that God’s people lied, concealed the truth, or provided false information in certain circumstances to protect their lives, support God’s people, and preserve their own lives. They were not bound to tell the truth morally because of the unwarranted sinful pressure and to avoid a higher evil. For example, Egyptian midwives lied to protect babies in Exodus 1:17-20. They were not condemned for their deception. Instead, God showed favor to them (Exodus 1:20).⁶ While God did not approve of their lie by any means, he approved their

² Davis, *Evangelical Ethics*, 11.

³ Davis, *Evangelical Ethics*, 11.

⁴ Samuel C. Storms, *Tough Topics 2: Biblical Answers to 25 Challenging Questions* (Fearn, Ross-shire, Scotland, Great Britain: Christian Focus Publications, 2015), 254-255.

⁵ Wayne A. Grudem, *Christian Ethics: An Introduction to Biblical Moral Reasoning* (Wheaton, Illinois: Crossway, 2018), 311.

⁶ Sam Storms, “Perplexing Passages: Do Exodus 1 and Joshua 2 Permit Christians to Lie? *TGC* (January 25, 2018), <https://www.thegospelcoalition.org/article/perplexing-passages-do-exodus-1-and-joshua-2-permit-christians-to-lie/>.

obedience in protecting the babies and his overall affirmation is evident. God did not prescribe a lie here, however, one could make the argument that God did not condemn it either. Similarly, Rahab had hidden the spies of Israel and lied to the king of Jericho (Judges 2:1-5). It is understandable that she lied in order to show her allegiance to Israel's God, and she demonstrated her faith (Hebrews 11:31). John Jefferson Davis opined that one human life is more important in God's sight than the entire world. He argued that her higher duty to protect God's servants prevented the *prima facie*, duty to tell the truth and her course of action was acceptable to God.⁷ In a similar vein, John Frame argued that we have no obligation to tell the truth to people who seek innocent life.⁸ In spite of the differences in semantics, a lie is either not addressed or it is pardoned, or it is not a lie at all in these circumstances.⁹

At last, the argument for not telling lies at all circumstances needs to be addressed. Augustine argued that one should never lie at all, since no examples of lies, deserving imitation, are found in the habits and deeds of saints.¹⁰ In a similar vein, Grudem argued that "...lying is always wrong in every situation and every circumstance of life, and this will be true for all eternity."¹¹ Although I affirm with Augustine and Grudem that lying is always sin and one should never lie, I also add that there are occasions deception or lie is permissible.¹² I believe that God shows compassion and pardons them as he did to the Egyptian midwives and Rahab. However, I

⁷ Davis, *Evangelical Ethics*, 10.

⁸ Grudem, *Christian Ethics*, 326.

⁹ Davis, *Evangelical Ethics*, 11.

¹⁰ Augustine, Roy J Deferrari, and Mary Sarah Muldowney. *Treatises on Various Subjects: The Christian Life, Lying, against Lying, Contenance, Patience, the Excellence of Widowhood, the Work of Monks, the Usefulness of Fasting, the Eight Questions of Dulcitus*, Fathers of the Church, a New Translation, V. 16 (repr., Washington, DC: Catholic University of America Press, 2002), 107.

¹¹ Grudem, *Christian Ethics*, 332.

¹² Storms, *Tough Topics 2*, 255.

do not affirm or endorse a lie and I believe that Christians should not be casual in their treatment of truth, even in the small areas.¹³

Conclusion

God is truth and every truth flows from the very nature of God. Therefore, a lie is not acceptable to him because it is contrary to his nature. Charles Hodge suggested that not every act of deception is a lie in terms of morality. According to him, a lie includes an intention to deceive when we are supposed and bound to tell the truth.¹⁴ However, there are instances in the Bible where people lied to protect life (Exod 1:17-20), support God's people (Josh 2), and to protect one's own life (2 Kgs 6:19). Bible did not condemn them for these lies. Instead of exposing them for their lies, God showed favor to midwives (Exod 1:20) and the author of Hebrews appreciated the faith of Rahab (Heb 11:31) by the inspiration of the Holy Spirit. As argued by John Frame, we have no moral obligation to tell the truth in certain circumstances. However, Christians should not be casual in their treatment of truth, even in the small areas.¹⁵

¹³ Storms, *Tough Topics 2*, 255.

¹⁴ Davis, *Evangelical Ethics*, 11.

¹⁵ Storms, *Tough Topics 2*, 255.

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